

Health and safety of Polish catering industry - law and practice

Bezpieczeństwo i higiena pracy w polskiej branży gastronomicznej - praktyka i prawo

Introduction

Every year, people all over the world have more and more free time. People spend much of this time in hotels, restaurants, resorts and cafés. The tourism industry is growing rapidly, especially the hotel and catering industry (HoReCa). Consequently, around 10 million people in Europe work in hotels, restaurants, pubs, pancake parlours and other places of leisure, accommodation and catering (5% of all employees). For example 10 % of Spaniards work in the HoReCa sector. Despite various perturbations brought about by epidemics, wars and poverty, the sector is constantly growing and developing (Eurofund, 2018, pp. 11–17; García-Madurga et al., 2021, pp. 6–15; Lock, 2021).

Catering services are an important component of HoReCa sector. Approximately 70 000 bars, restaurants, cafés, canteens and other catering establishments operate in Poland. Many of them are launched seasonally, usually in holiday resorts. However, more and more gastronomic facilities protect their brand and wish to be perceived as prestigious locations. Increasing numbers of guests also spend their leisure time after work or at weekends in evolving, esteemed restaurants or pubs. Alongside seasonal and prestige outlets, casual cafés, bars, eateries and dairy bars continue to develop. Noticeable among these are chain restaurants such as McDonald's or KFC (Kaszuba-Janus, 2021, pp. 6–55).

The good social atmosphere is the main reason why guests visit food courts. Certainly, it is also the taste of meals, good service and the restaurant's prestige. However, the key element of a good atmosphere in a restaurant or café is cleanliness, safety standards, high sanitary level and good labour and payment conditions for employees. Unless restaurateurs respect these rudimentary rules, food premises are unkempt, unsightly, dirty, and the crew is dissatisfied and unfriendly. Consequently, they are not visited by guests even when the food is delicious (Bilska et al., 2014, pp. 36–37).

Health and safety, sanitary standards (OSH) and labour law principles are paramount in catering business. Working with food and with customers requires compliance with the highest standards. Their violation leads not only to customer discouragement, but also, in the extreme scenario, to food poisoning or even consumer death. Therefore, Polish and international law regulations restrictively regulate the principles of food production. Moreover, legal regulations strictly indicate which health and safety rules and labour law principles have

to be observed to ensure a good atmosphere, order, hygiene and well-being in workplaces. Particularly in bars and cafés, their literal compliance is crucial.

Health and safety rules are strictly defined. Supposedly, they include such issues as: health and safety of employees and other company participants, e.g. contractors, entrepreneurs, co-workers, customers; fire safety; sanitary rules; occupational ergonomics and economics; occupational psychology; environmental safety; pension, disability, social security and corporate social responsibility. The essence of the concept of OSH is the broad safety of employees, customers and the catering establishment as a whole (Ambroziewicz et al., 2017).

Employees are the most important part of the health and safety system of any restaurant or bar. Their welfare determines the premises' proper operation, guests' satisfaction, and the restaurant's prestige. Counterintuitively, violations of health and safety rules and working conditions have a very negative impact on employees. If the level of inconvenience exceeds a certain limit, employees leave their jobs, work wrongly and transmit their dissatisfaction to customers. Therefore, the law very strongly determines all OSH rules related to employees.

The catering services market in Poland is growing rapidly despite pandemics and other perturbations. Meanwhile, the standard of services is rising. Nevertheless, it seems that employees are still being mistreated by restaurateurs. Particularly violated are working conditions and health and safety rules. Numerous pathologies occur in some places, significantly touching also the customers. Defective administrative and judicial supervision is unable to resolve rule violations. As a result, the industry may become highly stratified into prestigious locations where standards are respected and dysfunctional locations avoided by clients and potential employees (Zabrocki, 2012, pp. 75–82).

Methodology

The observation of certain types of catering establishments in Krakow, Czestochowa, Gdansk, Lublin, and Wroclaw, as well as discussions with employees of bars, restaurants, ice cream parlours, pubs, and sushi restaurants revealed numerous problems in HoReCa sector related to compliance with occupational health and safety (OSH), sanitary rules, and working conditions. The observation concerned many facilities from all over Poland, therefore the entire gastronomic sector was recognized to be affected by a large spectrum of OSH systemic problems.

Following the observation, decision to perform the present study was obvious. The primary objective was to describe the phenomena of compliance with OSH standards in catering

facilities in Poland (exploratory objective). Furthermore, it is important to explain the reasons why safety rules specified by Polish administrative and labour law as well as international regulations are not fully followed in foodservice facilities or its implementation is distorted (explicative objective). Finally, it is significant to present implementation proposals to improve health, safety and sanitary conditions in the Polish HoReCa industry along with proposals for appropriate legislative changes and enforcement of the law (implementation objective). Another important objective is to compare the postulative - normative status, reflected in legal acts with the empirical status (business reality). It is necessary to answer the question: whether the legal regulations correspond to the business needs and correlate with the reality, as well as whether the reality follows the legislator's recommendations.

The study is based on the main hypothesis: **in Polish catering establishments the OSH rules are not observed**. Moreover, health, safety and sanitary regulations do not influence Polish bars and restaurants. Finally, supervisory and control institutions for compliance with standards in the food industry are ineffective and impervious to problems.

The research has both a legal and sociological dimension. The legal research used Bernard Barelson's method of content analysis (Berelson, 1971). However, the results were analysed using the widespread in legal studies functional method. The functional method combines the principles of dogmatic and comparative analysis, as well as elements of historical-legal approach (Kędzierski, 2018, pp. 5–50).

Particular attention during the legal analyses focused on Polish administrative occupational safety and health acts as well as acts connected with sanitary safety, especially food safety. Implementation and executive acts were also important. The analysis of the Labour Code and other specific labour law acts was also undertaken (K. P, 1974), but their relevance is less visible here. Substantial attention has also been paid to acts of international law, particularly the conventions of the International Labour Organisation (ILO).

A sociological study was simultaneously conducted alongside the legal studies. The sociological study was conducted in the ground, among actual employees of Polish catering establishments. The method used here was semi-structured in-depth interviews (SSI) (Miński, 2017; Nicpoń & Marzęcki, 2010; Przybyłowska, 1978). However, the selection of research participants was made in an arbitrary (targeted) way. The selection aimed to identify experts who would be able to present health, safety and sanitary problems in catering establishments based on their experience as employees, but also as managers. Naturally, the empirical results obtained from expert testimonies do not have representativeness value. Nevertheless, they are

an ideal contribution to a broader and complete study (Babbie, 2008; Kvale, 2012; Sztabiński et al., 2005).

The interviews were conducted personally by the researcher during face-to-face meetings. The conversations were held between 14th July and 14th November 2021 in Wrocław, Katowice and Kraków. Research materials were archived for further use. The study was financed with own resources. The empirical part of this report was prepared based on the obtained data. This presentation is a complementary contribution to the main study focused on labour conditions in the gastronomy sector (Lipiec, 2021).

The sociological survey was conducted on an arbitrarily selected sample of twelve experts - employees and managers of the foodservice industry. All participants have at least 15 years of work experience in the HoReCa branch in several Polish cities (Gdańsk, Swidnica, Wrocław, Kraków, Katowice, Warszawa, Częstochowa, Lublin). They worked in different positions, in catering companies hiring from 1 to 50 employees, including McDonald's and AmRest (KFC) chain restaurants. However, their main experience was gained in smaller food service facilities with less than 20 employees, including contractors. Participants included eight men aged 28-35 years and four women aged 30-36 years. They all continue to work in the catering industry and have national and international experience¹.

Legal outline

Health, safety and sanitary rules in restaurants, pubs or bars are paramount for employees, employers, but also for guests and the public interest. Particularly in the HoReCa sector, ensuring an appropriate level of OSH is very important. Deficiencies in this area can easily lead to diseases and disasters associated with unhealthy food. Furthermore, it is particularly important to guarantee high health and safety standards for all employees. Working conditions in bars or restaurants are difficult and arduous, thus suitable protection from harmful factors, good employment and pay conditions and general safety are particularly important. Therefore, the food safety, food preparation, catering and the employees welfare should be subject to special state protection. Such protection should be reflected particularly through the introduction of appropriate and effective legislative solutions, but also through the current law application and enforcement in the case of infringements (Bukała et al., 2020, pp. 6–16; Grygiel-Kaleta, 2019, pp. 409–416; Kaźmierczak, 2009, pp. 11–13; Stankiewicz & Sznajder, 2010, pp. 10–64).

¹ The list and characteristics of study participants, interview recordings, notes, interview transcripts and codebase were archived for future study audit or further use.

Standards of occupational health and safety in Poland are mainly expressed through administrative law acts. The legislator introduces various acts and sub-legislative acts, regulating the principles of OSH in specific places, times and circumstances. Furthermore, comprehensive, supra-industry hygiene and safety conditions are established concerning food sanitary safety (Bezpieczeństwo Żywności, 2006), fire safety (Ochrona Przeciwpożarowa, 1991) or construction safety (Budowlane, 2003). Some legislation also provides complex rules for work safety and hygiene (Ogólne BHP, 1997). The introduced rules are accurate and cover most elements of internal and external safety and hygiene. Non-compliance with most of them is sanctioned by administrative penalties or criminal and civil liability (Ambroziewicz et al., 2017 *passim*; Krzyśków, 2014; Skowron, 2013, pp. 140–145; Widzisz, 2005, pp. 63–84). Some of the OSH principles are closely related to labour law principles, while others apply to specific places or circumstances more generally and independently of employees' involvement (Abramowski, 2020, pp. 221–375; Ambroziewicz et al., 2017, pp. 269-573,1453-1709).

Under the International Labour Organisation (ILO) principles, the provisions of occupational safety and health prevail over employees and work recipients and apply to the working environment, circumstances and working hours regardless of the legal or organisational form (Bulski, 2010; Ejdys, 2010, pp. 119–127). From the perspective of the HoReCa industry, the most relevant ILO conventions are: Convention 155 and Convention 161 on Occupational Safety and Health (Convention 161, 1985; Convention 155, 1981) and Convention 187 on Promotional Framework for Occupational Safety and Health (Convention 187, 2006). ILO Conventions cover many OSH issues at different levels. But basically, they only set frameworks and directives for the member states' legislation. Poland has acceded to most of these conventions (Jankowiak, 2007, pp. 110–121; Musiała & Jankowiak, 2007, pp. 36–37). ILO conventions are complemented by European Union legislation, particularly important for the food service sector are these related to food production (*OSH EU*, 2021; Koradecka, 2002, pp. 18–25; Zakrzewska-Szczepańska, 2003, pp. 23–29). International law acts have become the basis for the continuous development of Polish law on occupational safety and health, especially in catering sector.

Rules derived from international conventions and administrative acts apply to every person and every entity in a particular circumstance regardless of legal status. Practically the Minister of Labour and Social Policy in his regulation of 1997 on general rules of health and safety at work has indicated a number of detailed and universal OSH rules (Ogólne BHP, 1997). These rules are directed to places and circumstances of work performance. They do not apply

to people, but to things and situations: buildings, rooms and work procedures. Consequently, they obtain everyone present there.

From the perspective of Polish catering establishments, the most important legal acts regulated the principles of health, safety and hygiene are the aforementioned regulations and the act on food safety and nutrition (Bezpieczeństwo Żywności, 2006). Practical significance is also attached to the Parliament and Council (EU) Regulation of 2004 on the hygiene of foodstuffs (most commonly known as HACCP) (HACCP, 2004). Knowledge of these legal acts is the bible of every catering employee and restaurateur. They mainly shape the rules of kitchen work, not the rules of serving room operation, management, etc. Currently, there is no legal act in Polish or EU legislation that comprehensively regulates the conditions in the HoReCa industry, including catering operations. Entrepreneurs must follow their own intuition in OSH matters, the mentioned food acts and other general legal norms addressed to all sectors.

However, as health, safety and hygiene rules are dispersed throughout the food service industry, it is important to supervise compliance with national and international standards. Compliance with all health, safety and hygiene rules and working conditions is primarily supervised by the employees and their representative organisations (trade unions, works councils, social labour inspectors, OSH committees) (Baran et al., 2014, pp. 129–157, 411–494; Liszcz, 2019, pp. 2–11; Rutkowska, 2017, pp. 277–290; Szynal, 2020, pp. 78–86). Sometimes, however, employee supervision is insufficient. External, state supervision must be involved in such cases. Observance of OSH principles and working conditions in Polish catering facilities is monitored primarily by government inspections and labour courts. Potentially the most important in practice in the HoReCa industry are: State Labour Inspectorate (PIP), her main task is to supervise and monitor labour law compliance (PIP, 2007), and State Sanitary Inspectorate (commonly known as SANEPID), supervising compliance with specific health, safety and sanitary rules (SANEPID, 1985). Fire brigade inspection activities also significantly affect the compliance with safety rules in the catering industry. Supervision competencies over workplaces and employers are also exercised by other services, primarily by the Police and the Public Prosecutor's Office, the Social Insurance Institution (ZUS) and the National Tax Administration (KAS) (Ambroziewicz et al., 2017, pp. 100–265). Furthermore, in special situations, labour courts play a supervisory role (Tomaszewska, 2014).

Catering industry practice

Compliance with sanitary, occupational health and safety rules is extremely important in the gastronomic sector. Every restaurant guest (consumer) expects food prepared under sanitary

rules. Dirt in the kitchen or service space, rodents, spiders, fungi, stale products, diseased cooks, unpleasant smells are very harmful to consumers, employees and public safety. Their discovery by guests usually results in a public scandal and establishment liquidation.

Non-compliance with internal health and safety rules also has very negative consequences for employees. Improperly functioning kitchen machinery, improper pots, burners, fridges, insufficient aisles between rooms, improper fridge temperatures, lack of gloves and protective clothing for cooks, poor lighting, faulty knives can cause emergencies, fires, food poisoning and even death. Moreover, such problems may result in occupational diseases caused by heat or ionizing radiation. Any negative phenomena related to OSH result in a significant image damage to the restaurant, the negative reputation appearance among the community and, as a consequence, a bad opinion of the entire sector (Cieślik et al., 2010, pp. 567–571; Świątkowska et al., 2017, pp. 183–191).

Food and beverage businesses are strictly required to comply with all OSH rules, especially sanitary rules. However, following these rules is extremely difficult. On the one hand, bars and restaurants must strictly comply with similar rules to medical units, but on the other hand, they are staffed by unqualified people. Therefore, the health and safety reality is far from the legal model (Kasperek & Kondratowicz, 2020). Also, the legislator has very limited OSH requirements specific to the catering sector. Consequently, caterers must comply only with general administrative and labour law regulations. Occupational health and safety regulations for catering establishments are currently too vague and non-specialised, resulting in a lack of sector-specific rules (General food safety principles, 2002; HACCP, 2004; Bezpieczeństwo Żywności, 2006).

Bar and restaurant staff recognise the value of health and safety rules. They consider compliance with such rules as the most important element of the catering businesses. They emphasise that OSH is more important than the quality and taste of the prepared food. However, employees are not familiar with the detailed guidelines of labour law and administrative acts in this area. Everybody notices that in their workplaces particular attention is paid only to sanitary rules because of the sanctions fear for non-compliance. They also remark that the reality of compliance with health, safety and sanitary rules differs based on the catering facility's size.

Main problems

Ignorance and non-compliance with occupational health and safety standards leads to far-reaching malpractice and problems in foodservice establishments. Interviewees participating in the survey emphasise that workplace accidents occur regularly in foodservice locations.

Especially the kitchen crew regularly suffers from burns, too high temperatures, unpleasant smells. Furthermore, poor lighting, too low or too high equipment, transport too large goods to great heights, standing work, no protective clothing, no breaks, no safety goggles or gloves, no refreshment kits or water, no ventilation, no signage, no proper equipment dimensions, walkways or heights, inadequate storage conditions are common sins in the catering industry.

Employees are not trained in sanitary, OSH (initial and periodic training) and fire safety and are very occasionally medically examined. Training and safety procedures are performed in absentia simply by signing certificates by a doctor or fire and OSH specialists. Experts authorise or certify compliance with requirements without the employee participation or without visiting the business premises. Sometimes the documentation is actually falsified or purchased on the black market. They are fraudulent (*Gastronomia Ogłoszenia*, 2021; *Zakup fałszywej książeczki sanepidu*, 2021). Persistent non-compliance, circumvention and breaches of health and safety rules are caused by ignorance among employers and management, business premises cost-cutting and absence of external and internal supervision. Low and infrequent penalties for non-compliance and the employees' dependence on employers make it impossible to make changes in this area.

Respondents were asked specifically about compliance with specific health and safety and sanitary regulations at their workplace derived from the Labour Code and the Food Safety Act (*Bezpieczeństwo Żywności*, 2006; K. P, 1974). All unanimously agreed that their bosses do not follow practically any rules from the Code. Neither they personally nor the management know them. Even when accidents occur at work, the rules of the Labour Law are not respected. Apart from the selective observance of administrative sanitary regulations, especially in the consumption area, catering enterprises only ensure that employees have certificates for sanitary-epidemiological purposes, called "sanepid booklets" (Ambroziewicz et al., 2017, p. 594; Grudzińska, 2020; Kaczałek, 2021). Other rules are not observed. This applies to full-time employees as well as to persons engaged under civil law contracts. The failure to comply with OSH rules is equally severe and visible in both cases. The majority of indicated pathologies concern mainly small catering establishments, engaging a few employees. However, in larger places and chain restaurants, the situation is slightly different.

Chain and premium restaurants

Health and safety rules are often applied in large restaurants, mainly chain restaurants. Sometimes there are even dedicated occupational health and safety specialists. Especially in large restaurants, for example in the Am Rest chain (KFC, Pizza Hut) (*AmRest*, 2021) or

McDonald, the compliance with OSH rules is constantly monitored. A health and safety audit is performed even before the restaurant is opened. Large chain companies and prestigious restaurants often join voluntary associations regulating occupational safety or are subject to regular certification. Consequently, they follow certification processes, receiving a certificate of compliance with specific OSH standards, such as Code Alimentarius HACCP, or Bureau Veritas. Some catering companies also implement Polish and European sanitary safety standards for example HACCP or the ISO 22000:2018 standard (Cieslik et al., 2013, pp. 55–60). Nevertheless, these are voluntary certification processes, albeit part of the standards introduced by national or EU law. Occasionally, certification or the aspiration to meet certain standards is also observed among smaller bars or restaurants. However, this is a rare phenomenon associated with prestige of a quality restaurant (Chen et al., 2020, pp. 23–37; Ejdys, 2010, pp. 119–171; *Food Certification*, 2020; Turlejska, 2003; Wielgus, 2016).

The standard of compliance with public and voluntary health and safety rules in major catering establishments is much higher than in most small bars or restaurants. Interviewees emphasise that employees are trained in OSH and fire safety even before they start work in large catering units, and training is periodically repeated. There great importance is attached to signage and thermal radiation levels and odour standards. Also, supervision and external inspection by public services is more frequent than in smaller eateries, and there are audits from head office or external evaluators. A high standard of compliance with health and safety rules is thus maintained. Trade unions, health and safety committees and social labour services are also much more willing to report OSH problems.

However, despite the much higher standard of OSH compliance in large catering establishments, deficiencies still occur and accidents at workplace appear. Nevertheless, their scope and impact are slighter than in smaller foodservice facilities (*Praca w KFC - BHP*, 2019). The Polish catering services market is however dominated by smaller catering establishments. Consequently, most Polish ice cream parlours, beer halls, bars and canteens have widespread and profound problems with compliance with sanitary, occupational health and safety rules.

Compliance and supervision

The first word uttered by a gastronomy employee on rules of health and safety is the acronym SANEPID. Employees and managers are very much afraid of controls performed by inspectors of district sanitary-epidemiological stations, especially of potential administrative penalties, including temporary restaurant's shutdown. Afraid results especially from not following all sanitary, epidemiological and hygienic rules. Although fear of SANEPID inspections is

common, inspections have been rare in recent years, usually at the beginning of a restaurant's operation and as a result of complaints (Ambroziewicz et al., 2017, pp. 143–172, 1112–1115; Chrząszcz, 2021; *Co sprawdza Sanepid*, 2021; *Kontrola sanepidu*, 2021; Duchnowska, 2019, pp. 36–37; Kedzierski, 2015, pp. 46–47).

Survey participants note that the fear of sanitary inspection intervention is sometimes reasonable. As a rule, the employees and the management are not familiar with OSH rules, including fire safety or sanitary rules. Entrepreneurs are only vaguely acquainted with the regulations when launching production. Thereafter, they often ask external specialists for assistance to implement the rules. Knowledge of health and safety rules virtually disappears in further operations. Catering staff very often emphasize that the management only delegates to them the obligation to behave in accordance with the principles of OSH. Frequently people feel that the compliance depends solely on the more experienced employees, who alone do very little to ensure that health and safety rules are followed. The management of bars and restaurants follows the idea "somehow it will be done".

Almost every gastronomic outlet has a double standard of health and safety compliance. The first concerns those areas visible to the consumer. Typically, great care is exercised to cleanliness, signage, good atmosphere or the fulfilment of other rules in the customer service room. The reason for special care is the apparent care for customers, because compliance with OSH rules has an influence on their well-being and satisfaction, and consequently on the income and prestige of the location. The situation is completely different in kitchens and the backrooms. Adherence to the rules in those areas is not visible to customers and involves only the staff. Therefore, compliance with health and safety rules for the interior is secondary. Usually the OSH rules in this area are not known and are followed very selectively.

Non-compliance with health and safety rules regularly results in negative consequences for the management. Penalties imposed by the SANEPID are one of the most visible, and include decisions to suspend the business immediately. Nevertheless, the Inspectorate does not pay attention to most sanitary standards, but only to the most important and most clearly breached norms. Currently, the inspections very rarely decide of the temporary suspension, what mainly concern seasonal facilities. Violations of OSH rules actually remain beyond the interest of public supervision and monitoring services because of the negligible activity of the National Labour Inspectorate (Sienkiewicz, 2020, pp. 123–125; Wojciechowski, 2011, pp. 67–86).

The interviewees actually do not notice other forms of working conditions supervision and monitoring. They know that the National Labour Inspectorate (PIP) exists, but they have never personally encountered its activities; nor has the PIP visited any of their workplaces in the last 15 years. Similarly, no pressure can be felt from the inspectorate on employers, who are not afraid to apply supervisory and monitoring actions toward them. From the point of view of the catering establishments, this authority is a hypothetical entity with no current influence upon their operations. Undoubtedly, far-reaching labour law infringements in food service facilities are one of the consequences of this situation.

The external supervision of the fire department, the police, the Office of Competition and Consumer Protection (UOKiK) and the trade inspection, as well as other guards, agencies, inspections, etc., is completely invisible in catering business. The employees have never noticed any inspections performed by other investigators. Neither do they feel any pressure, fear, respect towards the monitoring bodies and external supervision. Management also does not feel supervision from public authorities. The real or mental presence of other supervisory bodies in the operation of catering units is purely illusory. The supervisory and monitoring competences of the various specialised bodies are actually not executed or are unnoticeable in daily business practice.

Internal and judicial supervision

People working in the catering industry regularly complain about non-compliance with health and safety rules and violations of working conditions: abuse of civil law contracts by employers, lack of leave, abrupt and immediate termination of employment, too much workload, or employment discrimination. Apparently, employees experiencing such practices would regularly appeal to the National Labour Inspectorate (PIP) or labour courts to intervene in their cases. However, this is not the case.

Survey participants emphasise that bar and restaurant staff are actually completely unfamiliar with the labour courts. Those who have heard something about it vehemently and systemically do not want to use its assistance. Interviewees emphasise that sophisticated court procedures, potential court costs and the necessity of a high commitment effectively deter them from looking for protection in labour courts. The most aware employees emphasise that they are unable to gather adequate evidence to support their hypotheses, while colleagues would not be eager to testify in fear of losing their jobs. The common belief is even in the case of a positive labour court decision, the employer would still do everything to punish and discharge the recalcitrant employee. Respondents highlight that the temporary nature of catering job and the

large-scale students deployment make pointless to use the judicial procedure to supervise working conditions. The employees are leaving their jobs quickly anyway, thus they do not want to get embroiled in long-term litigation. The greatest punishment for the employer by an employee whose rights are violated is simply to leave immediately without court involvement.

However, interviewees report that during their 15 years in various catering businesses, they have twice encountered an employee using court proceedings to force the employer to behave in accordance with the law. Firstly, the case related to the employer's requirement to issue a labour certificate, and secondly the recognition of the civil law contract as a *de facto* employment contract. The labour court ordered the employer to issue an employment certificate in the first case, but the employer did not do it. Meanwhile, in the second case, the court found that employment under civil law contracts in catering establishments is standard and decided not to recognise the civil law contract as an employment relationship.

Employees' stories suggest that in bars, ice cream and pancake parlours, the most effective means are personal supervision to ensure that working conditions, wages, OSH and sanitary conditions are observed. Interviewees emphasise that any collective influence on employers is not very effective. Therefore, supervision by trade unions would not be very effective. The lack of sectoral trade unions means that this possibility of influence does not even currently exist.

However, in case of extreme violation of health and safety rules and working conditions, a very strong employee argument is the possibility of immediate termination of the relationship (abandonment). The constant reminder to the employer's representatives of health and safety regulations, labour law standards and contractual conditions also plays an important role. Also an important individual supervision measure is the management's threat of non-performance of specific tasks and duties. Such countermeasures in case of non-compliance with the rules have an immediate effect, although they can be risky for the employee.

Although the application of personal forms of employee supervision is not as successful. Occasionally, it only works after many months of the managers threatening or obstructing work. In practice, these are the only enforcing means of proper and beneficial behaviour on employers. When bosses threaten to intervene with the sanitary inspection or labour inspection, or claim a case in the labour court, they often respond with laughter and release difficult and conflictual employees.

Unfortunately, in the gastronomic industry the system of administrative, judicial, trade union and private supervision and monitoring does not exist, while its remnants are impaired. Consequently, numerous negative phenomena in the area of OSH, compliance with

sanitary standards, labour law regulations and contractual conditions are not noticed, condemned, monitored, supervised and fixed. The catering industry pathologies are also exacerbated by the absence of an effective monitoring system. State authorities and judicial bodies are virtually paralysed and highly ineffective. Meanwhile, employees want a peaceful and well-paid job, hence they do not force employers to behave correctly in accordance with labour and administrative law. Consequently, the problems remain and are compounded. Nevertheless, the situation will not change until employees and state supervisory and monitoring bodies become more aware and effective.

Conclusions

Occupational health, safety and sanitary rules are only followed at random Polish HoReCa facilities. Catering entrepreneurs generally choose only those rules to follow that are profitable, other are simply ignored. A similar situation applies to staff. Only those standards are respected resulting in the apparent guest satisfaction. Unfortunately, this situation is accepted by the catering establishments' organisers, employees, but also by the clients. Nobody cares that all OSH standards are strictly observed. Compliance with them is still determined by the entrepreneur's economic calculation and the customer's apparent and relative satisfaction. This is a very dismal observation, because such a compromise leads to law violations and long-term visitor dissatisfaction, personnel problems and real work-related accidents and mishaps. Putting the economic account and apparent tranquillity above compliance is not worth it in the long-term.

The staff of cafés, restaurants and pubs are particularly involved in OSH compliance problems. They can see their bosses not enforcing the legal provisions in this area not only towards them, but also towards their guests and the whole enterprise. However, they do little to change this situation. They also benefit from apparent safety, but are partly responsible for breaking the law. Occasionally violations of OSH rules result in payback. Most frequently this is related to work accidents, overtime work, social security and sickness, and sporadically the need to pay fines for non-compliance with sanitary rules. Very occasionally, employees also have to enforce their rights in public institutions or labour courts.

Labour and OSH law standards very strictly regulate safety, hygiene and sanitary rules of catering establishments. However, the multitude of regulations overwhelms catering staff and managers. Actually, no restaurateur or employee, even the most aware, educated and virtuous is able to fulfil all OSH, sanitary, working conditions and other safety rules. Consequently, these rules are overlooked, forgotten, unknown or simply broken. Even the most

significant standards are unnoticed by all actors of bars' or restaurants' life in the plethora of legal norms. The consequence is the elimination of these non-essential regulations from the gastronomic community's consciousness.

Undoubtedly, it would be right to create a comprehensive law for the catering and hotel industry. Specifically, such a law should compile current provisions on tourism and the hotel industry (Imprezy Turystyczne, 2017; Usługi Hotelarskie, 1997), as well as OSH and employee regulations, consult the specific sector character. However, it is necessary to compile labour law, administrative law, as well as EU and ILO legislation. Implementation a comprehensive law would facilitate operations in the HoReCa sector, adapt regulations to the sector specifics and enable fast and effective verification and supervision of compliance with statutory principles. The inclusion of these standards in a single act would create a clear and simple normative system for the entire industry, with a prominent place for health, safety and sanitary standards.

Furthermore, more attention should be paid to the employee and entrepreneur education on safety, hygiene, labour law and sanitary rules. Such education should be continuous training and instruction in the workplace. Preferably, sanitary inspectors or labour inspectors should visit bars and restaurants and demonstrate proper safety rules. Probably the right solution would also be professional workshops to instruct the crew how to properly manage a restaurant or work there. NGOs or branch organisations could provide this competence-building under the umbrella of public resources. Permanent and real change can only be achieved by improving competences.

Naturally, supervision and monitoring of OSH rules in gastronomic facilities are equally important. Particularly important here is the improvement of the state supervision system of the labour inspection, trade inspection and the sanitary inspection. Supervisors need to visit various locations more often and instruct staff members on legal compliance. Ultimately, they should not evade punishing offenders or even closure of facilities. Police and preventive measures are unfortunately necessary if soft training and admonition methods do not succeed. More inspectors should work in the field, receive better remuneration and be independent. However, without an effective supervisory and monitoring system, pathologies will continue to appear.

Employees and their representatives supervision of the catering facilities should also be stimulated by authorities. However, for higher efficiency is very important to reduce the junk contracts and to improve the working conditions and salaries. Otherwise, employees will be in constant fear of being expelled as a result of complying with all safety standards.

Regrettably, the questions and hypotheses proposed at the introduction tend to be confirmed. Generally, health, safety and sanitary rules are not observed in Polish catering establishments. If they are, it happens only selectively and depending on the economic benefits. Familiarity with the law among employees and management is mediocre, which results in a lack of significant impact of OSH administrative standards on Polish catering businesses. They live their own lives, most often separated from the objectively valid legal norms. As a result of the defective public supervision, real-time supervision of restaurants is very illusory. Health, safety and sanitary regulations also are not adequate to the needs of the HoReCa sector. They are elaborate, dispersed, unclear, fossilised and not suited to this particular industry. Consequently, they do not correspond to the reality of this very dynamic and flexible economy sector.

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